

The Influence of Hypertension Patient Satisfaction on Post Covid19 Telepharmacy at Tanralili Puskesmas, Maros Regency

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ABSTRACT

Patient satisfaction is the patient's expectations arising from the actions of health workers as a result of the performance of health services during the process of interacting in an effort to provide services. At the end of 2019 the world was shocked by the spread of Covid-19 so social restrictions were put in place which resulted in decreased service performance and could affect patient satisfaction. This problem can be overcome by improving health services, namely telepharmacy. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of hypertension patient satisfaction on post-Covid-19 telepharmacy services at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros Regency. The type of research used in this research is non-experimental, with a descriptive quantitative method and prospective data collection in the form of a questionnaire. Sampling used a purposive sampling technique with samples that met the inclusion criteria for hypertension patients at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros Regency, who had received telepharmacy and were willing to fill out a questionnaire. The results of the research on the satisfaction of hypertensive patients with post-covid-19 telepharmacy at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros district, namely the reliability aspect (97.2%), the responsiveness aspect (98.93%), and the empathy aspect (95.6%) which is the value of the level of satisfaction of respondents to telepharmacy provided by Pharmacy Staff. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that hypertensive patients are very satisfied with receiving telepharmaceuticals, which can be seen from the percentage of satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Satisfaction, Telepharmaceuticals, Hypertension.

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INTRODUCTION

The current Covid-19 pandemic creates many challenges and opportunities for health workers, especially pharmacists, to improve and expand the practice of pharmaceutical services. One of them is providing telepharmaceutical services or providing medical services using telephone technology or video chat (Wifaaq, *et al.*, 2021).

In accordance with the development of science and technology, in the health sector, the orientation of the pharmaceutical industry has changed from managing drugs as a commodity to full service (pharmacy management) in the sense that it does not only provide drugs, but also broad intelligence, including providing information to support the use of drugs that are correctly and rationally, monitoring the use of drugs and the possibility of medication errors. Pharmacists must understand the needs of patients as an effort to meet those

needs and increase patient satisfaction for the services provided (Ministry of Health RI 2019).

World Health Organization (WHO) data for 2018 shows that around 1.13 billion people worldwide experience high blood pressure, which means that one in three people in the world diagnosed with high blood pressure increases every year, it is estimated that every year 10.44 million people died from high blood pressure and its complications (Ministry of Health RI, 2019).

based on results research conducted by Wibowo (2018) and section 5 namely trust, reciprocity, trust, empathy and clear evidence that pharmacies do not pay attention to a complete and safe environment for patients, employees often forget to provide information about foods to avoid when taking medication and provide information. activities to avoid drug-related problems, slow service to patients and employees who do not provide satisfactory service to consumers.

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In previous research, Rahmawati and Wahyuningsih (2016) mentioned a relationship and significance between pharmaceutical services and patient satisfaction in health care facilities.

Based on this, researchers are interested in conducting this study which aims to determine the effect of telepharmacy-based hypertensive patient satisfaction after Covid-19 at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros Regency. It is hoped that the results of this study can be used as documentation and evaluation material for services by both health workers and pharmacy staff.

RESEARCH METHOD

Types of research

The type of research used in this research is *non-* experimental, with quantitative methods and prospective data collection. The sample collection technique namely

Purposive sampling is a sampling technique that has certain considerations or is based on criteria selected by researchers according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria (Sugiyono, 2016).

The sample used in this study is a sample that meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The inclusion criteria are patients who are willing to fill out a questionnaire, patients diagnosed with hypertension, patients aged 40-80 years, patients who have received telepharmacy from pharmacists or researchers.

While the exclusion criteria were patients who temporarily stopped running the study, patients who were not diagnosed with hypertension, patients <40 years and >80 years, patients who did not receive telepharmacy from pharmacists or researchers.

Research procedure

1. Preparation

- a. Determining Population and Sample.

1. The results of my validity test are esioner

Test Table validity of the reliability questionnaire _

Question Items	Results		To the conclusion
	R count	R table	
X 1	0,799	0,549	Valid
X 2	0,735	0,549	Valid
X3	0,724	0,549	Valid
X4	0,871	0,549	Valid
X5	0,850	0,549	Valid
Y1	0,562	0,549	Valid
Y2	0,654	0,549	Valid
Y3	0,743	0,549	Valid
Z1	0,711	0,549	Valid
Z2	0,646	0,549	Valid

Based on the data from the test results in the table above, it is known that out of the 10 question items , all questions were

- b. Determine the number of patients who meet the inclusion criteria
 - c. Develop a structured questionnaire through literature study.
- #### 2. Implementation Stage
- a. Take care of permits for study programs, and take permits from the health office and ask for approval to research at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros Regency
 - b. Then test the validity and reliability of the questionnaire before the questionnaire is distributed.
 - c. After all the questionnaires meet the valid or reliable requirements, the questionnaires can be given to patients.
 - d. The implementation phase includes collecting research data on patients at the Tanralili Health Center who have received previous pharmaceutical digitization services by researcher 1.
 - e. Patients were asked for prior consent before filling out the questionnaire. If the patient is willing, then he can fill in the personal data contained on the consent sheet.
 - f. The completion stage includes processing the data obtained from the results of the patient data questionnaire which is processed using the SPSS application.

analytical method

The method of analysis of this research is using a questionnaire and processed using SPSS. The tests carried out were the Chi-Square test and the One-Sample Test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validation Test Results

Validation Test i is a test conducted to reveal something that will be measured by the questionnaire. It is declared valid or valid if the result of the calculated r value is greater than r, namely 0.549 (Ghozali, 2016).

The validity test in this study used a sample of 30 respondents from patients seeking treatment at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros Regency.

declared valid. The decision-making method used in this study was to compare the calculated R value from the SPSS output

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with the R table value for the 30 respondents, which was 0.549, which means that the correlation of the 10 item items was declared valid because R count > R table (0.549).

Reliability Test Results

Reliability test is an index that shows the extent to which the instrument can be trusted or relied upon. It is said that a questionnaire is reliable or reliable if the Alpha-Cronbach value is > 0.60 (Mathar, 2018).

2. Questionnaire reliability test results

Table of results of the reliability test of the questionnaire

Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
10	0.921	Reliable

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the 10 item statements are reliable because the results obtained are a large alpha value of 0.921. So it can be concluded that reliability is due to the Alpha-Cronbach value > 0.60.

Research result

1. Table of Characteristics of Respondents with Hypertension

Table 11. Characteristics of research respondents

No	Characteristics of respondents	N	Persentase
1	Gender		
	Woman	26	52%
	Man	24	48%
2	Age (Years)		
	40-59	32	64
	61-80 (Geriatric)	18	36
	Total	50	100%

Based on table 11 above, the results showed that there were 26 female respondents (52 %) and 24 male respondents (48 %). The characteristics of the respondents in this study were 32 respondents at the age of 40-60 years, while at the age of 61-80 years there were 18 respondents . In the age group of the respondents above, the age group that the most was found in the age category of 40 -60 years, namely as many as 32 respondents. As for the results of a study conducted at the Pinang City Hospital, it was found that the number of hypertensive patients with female sex dominated, namely as many as 52% and male sex as much as 48% (Sylvia & Pasaribu, 2021). According to a survey by the National Health Agency (2018) that high blood pressure is more at risk for women than men. Female sex is more at risk of experiencing an increase in

blood pressure due to the hormone estrogen (Dagmar *et al* ., 2021).

The hormone estrogen is a hormone that has an effect on blood pressure and the development of hypertension by functioning as a protector so that fat accumulation does not occur (atherosclerosis). Atherosclerosis is what will cause hypertension. The hormone estrogen can cause *High Density Lipoprotein* (HDL) levels to be higher so that it will prevent fat accumulation. Age is very influential on hormones, so that as women get older they will gradually lose the hormone estrogen. This estrogen hormone will function to protect blood vessels from damage. Therefore, if there is a decrease in the level of the hormone estrogen, women are more susceptible to hypertension (Dagmar *et al* ., 2021).

2. Table of Respondents' Satisfaction (Reliability) with Telepharmaceuticals

Table 12. Results of the percentage of answers (Reliability) of respondents

No	Statement	TP	KP	CP	P	SP
		Percentage (%)				
A	reliability					
1 .	The pharmacist explains the illness patient properly and clearly	0 0%	0 0%	2 4%	2 4%	46 92%
2 .	Pharmacists tell how to treat of the patient's disease	0 0%	1 2%	2 4%	3 6%	44 88%

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3.	Pharmacy staff provide counseling, education to the patient	0 0%	0 0%	3 6%	8 16%	39 78%
4.	Pharmacists remind patients to take the medicine	0 0%	0 0%	4 8%	2 4%	44 88%
5.	Pharmacy personnel provide drug information with easy to understand language	0 0%	0 0%	1 2%	3 6%	46 92%

Information :

- Very satisfied (SP) : 5
- Satisfied (F) : 4
- Satisfied enough (CP) : 3
- Dissatisfied (KP) : 2
- Not Satisfied (TP) : 1

Based on table 12 above, the results of the highest percentage of respondents' answers were "SP" or Very Satisfied at X1 (92%) with 46 respondents, at X2 (88%) with 44 respondents, at X3 (78%) the number of respondents 39 people, X4 (88%) with a total of 44 people, and finally at X5 (92%) with a total of 46 respondents. In the results table above, for the value of

respondents' satisfaction about (Reliability) on the influence of telepharmacy use satisfaction, namely the average Hypertension respondent answered Very Satisfied with Telepharmaceutical services provided by pharmacists with an average percentage of 78% -90% and the highest was 92 %.

2. Table of Respondents' Satisfaction (Responsiveness) to Telepharmaceuticals

Table 13. Results of the percentage of answers (responsiveness) of respondents

No	Statement	TP	KP	CP	P	SP
		Percentage (%)				
B. responsiveness						
1.	Pharmacy personnel are able to serve patients with quick and precise	0 0%	0 0%	1 2%	4 8%	45 90%
2.	Pharmacists always provide feedback regarding patient complaints	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	50 100%
3.	Pharmacy personnel are responsive in responding to patients who inquire via online (whatsApp)	0 0%	0 0%	1 2%	0 0%	49 98%

Based on table 13 above, the results of the highest percentage of respondents' answers were "SP" or Very Satisfied at Y1 (90%) with 45 respondents , at Y2 (100%) with 50 respondents, at Y3 (98%) the number of respondents 49 people. In the results table above, for the value of respondents' satisfaction about

(responsiveness) to the influence of satisfaction on the use of telepharmacy, namely the average hypertensive respondent answered very satisfied with the telepharmacy services provided by the pharmacy staff with the highest percentage, namely 100% with a total of 50 respondents

3. Table of Respondents' Satisfaction (Empathy) for Telepharmaceuticals

Table 14. Results of the percentage of respondents' answers (Empathy).

No	Statement	TP	KP	CP	P	SP
		Percentage (%)				
C. Empathy						
1.	Pharmacy personnel always behave friendly and courteous in serving patients	0 0%	0 0%	3 6%	6 12%	41 82%
2.	Are you satisfied with the existence of digital services	0	0	3	5	42

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online or make it easier for you to consult distance Far. 0% 0% 6% 10% 84%

Based on table 14 above, the results of the highest percentage of respondents' answers, namely "SP" or Very Satisfied at Z1 were (82%) with 41 respondents, in Z2 (84%) with 42 respondents. In the results table above, for the value of respondents' satisfaction about (Empathy) on the effect of

telepharmacy use satisfaction, namely the average Hypertension respondent answered Very Satisfied with Telepharmaceutical services provided by pharmacists with a low percentage (82%) with 41 respondents and the highest was 42% with a total of 42 respondents.

Table 15. Analysis of the effect of hypertensive patient satisfaction on telepharmacy

Category	Sample (n)	Percentage (%)	p value
SP	446	8.92 %	
P	33	0,66 %	
CR	18	0,36 %	0,000
KP	1	0,02 %	
TP	0	0,%	

The results of the one sample test statistical analysis obtained an average hypertension patient satisfaction in the dimensions of reliability, responsiveness, empathy at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros Regency, namely the p value obtained 0.00 <0.05, meaning that there is a relationship or influence of hypertension patient satisfaction on telepharmacy in reliability, responsiveness, and empathy variables. This proves that good quality pharmaceutical digitalization health services will increase patient satisfaction. Good service quality has a positive impact on patient recovery in accordance with the nature of the basic service of health services is to meet the needs and demands of users of health services.

CONCLUSION

The results of the research on the satisfaction of hypertensive patients with post-covid-19 telepharmacy at the Tanralili Health Center, Maros district, namely the reliability aspect (97.2%), the responsiveness aspect (98.93%), and the empathy aspect (95.6%) which is the value of the level of satisfaction of respondents to telepharmacy provided by Pharmacy Staff. Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that hypertensive patients are very satisfied with receiving telepharmaceuticals, which can be seen from the percentage of satisfaction.

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